

Effects of microplastics on aquatic life, invertebrate plastic degradation, plant growth, and human cells

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ABSTRACT

Microplastic pollution is an urgent environmental issue with widespread impacts on biological systems. This study examines the effects of microplastics on seed germination and early growth of barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) and perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.), the biodegradation of polystyrene by mealworms (*Tenebrio molitor* Linnaeus, 1758), and the cytotoxicity of mealworm-derived excreta on human cells. Barley and ryegrass seeds were exposed to microplastics of varying sizes, surface charges, and concentrations to assess their impact on germination and growth patterns. Water fleas (*Daphnia* spp.) were exposed to microplastics to evaluate their survival under varying conditions. Additionally, mealworms were fed polystyrene to evaluate their ability to degrade plastics to obtain the excreta possibly containing digested plastics. The cytotoxicity of mealworm excreta was assessed on human Caco-2 cells using WST-8 viability assays. This integrated approach provides new insights into the ecological and cellular effects of microplastic pollution and highlights the potential of mealworm biodegradation as a plastic waste management strategy.

KEYWORDS: Microplastics, *Hordeum vulgare* (barley), *Lolium perenne* (perennial ryegrass), Mealworm, Water flea, Caco-2

1. INTRODUCTION

Plastic pollution has emerged as a critical environmental challenge, with microplastics—tiny particles less than 5 mm in size—posing a significant threat due to their ability to infiltrate ecosystems and affect biological processes. The chemical composition of microplastics varies and includes common polymers such as polyethylene (PE), polystyrene (PS), polypropylene (PP), and polyvinyl chloride (PVC). As the modern society produces vast amounts of plastics every day (413.8 million tonnes worldwide in year 2023 according to Plastics Europe¹, secondary microplastics formed through the degradation of larger plastic waste are also prevalent. In addition, a variety of consumer products such as cosmetics and personal care items contain microplastics as ingredients². Once in the environment, microplastics interact with plants, animals, and microorganisms, disrupting ecological balance and raising concerns about their long-term effects on human and environmental health³. This study takes a comprehensive approach to understand the impacts of microplastics on various biological systems, including plants, aquatic organisms, insects, and human cells.

Plants, as the foundation of terrestrial ecosystems and agriculture, are particularly susceptible to environmental stressors such as microplastics⁴. Direct impact of microplastics on plant growth include reduced seed germination, as well as decreased root and shoot length^{5,6}. Accumulation of microplastics in the leaves via transport from soil through xylem was also reported in leaf lettuce⁷. Possible mechanisms of these reduced growth are oxidative damage⁸, alteration in gene expression profile⁹, and reduced chlorophyll contents¹⁰.

Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) and perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.) were selected for this research due to their agricultural importance and their contrasting growth patterns, which offer insights into how microplastics might affect diverse plant species. Seed germination and early growth stages are critical periods in a plant's life cycle, and exposure to environmental contaminants during these stages can have cascading effects on overall plant health and productivity. This study evaluates how microplastics of different sizes, surface charges, and concentrations influence the germination, root elongation, and shoot growth of barley and ryegrass. By understanding these effects, this research aims to elucidate the potential risks posed by microplastics to terrestrial ecosystems and food security.

Aquatic ecosystems are another major victim of plastic pollution, with microplastics entering water bodies through various sources, including industrial discharge, agricultural runoff, and household waste¹¹. Freshwater organisms like water fleas (*Daphnia* spp.) are particularly vulnerable to these contaminants. Due to its easy access and manipulation, water fleas have been used to research toxic effects of microplastics^{12,13}. As a keystone species in certain aquatic ecosystems, *Daphnia* spp. plays an essential role in maintaining freshwater ecosystem stability and serves as a bioindicator for water quality. This study investigates the survival rates of water fleas when exposed to microplastics of varying sizes, surface charges, and concentrations. The findings provide valuable data on how microplastics affect aquatic ecosystems and the potential risks to freshwater biodiversity and food webs.

In addition to their ecological impacts, microplastics have sparked interest for their interactions with organisms capable of breaking down plastics. Mealworms (*Tenebrio molitor* Linnaeus, 1758), a larval form of the darkling beetle, have been identified as a potential solution for plastic waste management due to their ability to consume and biodegrade polystyrene⁴. Previous studies have focused on the direct effects of plastics on mealworms themselves, but the study regarding any toxic effects of the excreta from mealworms fed with plastics has not been reported. In this study, we examined any potential cytotoxic effects of mealworm-derived byproducts from polystyrene on human cells. Human health concerns arise not only from direct exposure to microplastics but also from the byproducts of their degradation¹⁴. In this research, Caco-2 cells, a model of human intestinal epithelium, were exposed to solutions derived from mealworm excreta processed through organic solvents. Cell viability assays were conducted to evaluate whether the degradation products produced by mealworms pose any risks to human health. This investigation bridges the gap between environmental and human health concerns, emphasizing the importance of assessing microplastics and their byproducts across biological systems.

By integrating plant, aquatic, insect, and cellular systems, this study aims to provide a holistic understanding of the biological impacts of microplastics. It highlights the multifaceted risks associated with microplastics while exploring potential mitigation strategies, such as mealworm biodegradation, to address the global plastic pollution crisis. Through this multi-pronged approach, the research contributes to the growing body of knowledge needed to tackle the complex challenges posed by plastic waste.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Microplastics

All the microplastics were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. They are fluorescent-labelled polystyrene latex beads with either positive (amine-modified) or negative (carboxylate- or sulfate-modified) surface charge. The product numbers for 100 nm ones are L9904 (amine-modified, fluorescent orange), L9902 (sulfate-modified, fluorescent red), for 1000 nm ones are L4655 (carboxylate-modified, fluorescent yellow-green), L9654 (amine-modified, fluorescent orange), and for 2000 nm ones are L0280 (amine-modified, fluorescent blue), L3030 (carboxylate-modified, fluorescent red).

2.2 Plant Research Methods

Barley seeds and ryegrass seeds were soaked in water for one day to help their germination. The soaked seeds were exposed to microplastics to evaluate the potential impact of plastic particles on growth rate. The five (for barley) or six (for ryegrass) seeds were placed in each well, treated with 2 mL distilled water containing 2% of microplastic particles with sizes of 100 nm, 1000 nm, and 2000 nm. As a control, distilled water without any microplastics was used. The seeds of each condition were put on wet gauze for 12 days at room temperature. The plant growth was observed by measuring the weight and stem length of the germinated seeds. Additionally, roots were washed in ethanol and observed under the fluorescence microscope to detect microplastic particles with fluorescent tags. Pictures of the cut parts and root tips were taken.

2.3 Daphnia (water flea) Research Methods

Daphnia spp. were cultured in a medium prepared with 8 mg/L KCl, 120 mg/L MgSO₄, 120 mg/L CaSO₄·2H₂O, and 192 mg/L NaHCO₃ in distilled water. They were maintained at room temperature under ambient conditions in the laboratory.

The study aimed to determine the impact of microplastics on the survival rates of water fleas. In each well of a 6-well culture plate, 1 ml of culture medium containing *Daphnia* spp. was added. To introduce microplastics, 10, 15, or 20 µL of microplastic beads were added to each well containing *Daphnia* spp. for 2 days of incubation. The survival rate of the water fleas was determined by manual counting of living animals with their typical jerky and hopping motion in water. Three sets of independent experiments were conducted, each using a different range of animal numbers per condition: 14 ~ 43 in the first set, 5 ~ 10 in the second set, and 7 ~ 22 in the third set. In each set of experiment, the percentage of live water fleas out of total number was calculated. The average percentages from the three experimental sets were plotted.

2.4 Mealworm Research Method

The mealworm (*Tenebrio molitor*) experiments were designed to investigate the biodegradation of plastic and its subsequent effects on biological systems. Mealworms were divided into two distinct groups to compare the outcomes of traditional feeding and plastic exposure: Group A (Control Group): Mealworms were fed with a standard diet consisting of bran and fresh cucumber. This group served as the control to observe normal mealworm metabolism and excreta. Group B (Experimental Group): Mealworms were fed only with Styrofoam cubes of 5 cm. Both groups of mealworms were maintained in closed containers at room temperature under the ambient conditions. The excreta from both groups were collected and stored at -20°C before further experiments.

2.5 Caco-2 cell Research Method

Excreta collected from both mealworm groups—Group A (fed with bran and cucumber) and Group B (fed exclusively with Styrofoam without any other foods)—were processed to prepare solutions for cell viability testing. The excreta from each group were mixed with either dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) or ethanol (EtOH) to facilitate the extraction of any bioactive or chemical compounds. This resulted in four primary treatment solutions: DMSO + Excretion A (excreta from group A), ethanol + Excretion A, DMSO + Excretion B (excreta from group B), and ethanol + Excretion B. For each combination, we used either 15 mg or 30 mg of excreta. The excreta were added to 500 ml of DMSO or ethanol and vortexed for 1 minute, followed by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes. The supernatant 200 to 300 µL was withdrawn and subjected to further centrifugation at 12300 rpm for 5 minutes to completely remove any solids. Solutions were stored at -20 °C before use. Additionally, DMSO and ethanol alone were used as controls to account for any solvent-related effects.

Caco-2 cells were cultured in a standard cell culture environment at 37°C with 5% CO₂ in a humidified incubator for three days. Cells were seeded into 96-well plates at a consistent density to ensure uniform growth across all wells. Upon reaching the appropriate confluency, the cells were

treated with the prepared excreta solutions. Each solution, along with the solvent controls (DMSO and ethanol alone), was applied to the cells at multiple concentrations to evaluate potential dose-dependent effects. The viability of the treated cells was assessed using a colorimetric assay WST-8, which is a water-soluble chemical that is reduced by active dehydrogenase enzyme present in living cells. Upon reduction by dehydrogenase, WST-8 becomes an orange-colored formazan that has absorbance at 450 nm light. The more living cells are present, the more orange-colored WST-8 are observed in the microplate reader. For 100 μ L medium in each well of the 96-well plate, 10 μ L WST-8 reagent was added and the cells were incubated for one hour to facilitate the reduction reaction.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To examine the effects of microplastics on the plant growth, microplastics with different diameter and surface charge (negative or positive) were added to the germinating plant barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) and ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*). After 12 days of growing at room temperature, the fresh weight and stem length were measured (Figure 1). Microplastics did not decrease the growth of ryegrass, but they slightly increased the growth of barley seedling. This increase tends to be more with smaller-sized microplastics. The largest increase of growth was observed with 100 nm microplastics and the smallest increase of growth was observed in the plants incubated with 2000 nm microplastics (Figure 1, upper panel). Since this experiment was done once, more experiments should be done to confirm that this is the significant increase.

We then investigated whether microplastics were taken up by the plants. Since all the microplastics had fluorescence tagging, roots of barley were observed under the fluorescence microscope. Except for the 2000 nm microplastics with positive charge, all other microplastics were found inside the root (Figure 2). The excitation and emission for fluorescent tag of the 2000 nm microplastics are approximately 360 nm and 420 nm, respectively. Therefore, it could not be detected under the current setting of the fluorescence microscope. In summary, microplastics seemed to be taken up by the plant roots and affect the plant growth depending on the plant species. Still, the presence of microplastics in the root did not seem to decrease or inhibit the plant growth.

Microplastics often slip into the aquatic system such as ponds, rivers, and finally ocean. To investigate the possible impact of microplastics on the aquatic lives, microplastics were added to the culture solution of water fleas. The smallest microplastics with 100 nm size and positive charge greatly decreased the survival rate of *Daphnia* spp. in a dose-dependent manner (Figure 3). In all three independent sets of experiments, none of the water fleas survived when exposed to 20 μ L of 100 nm microplastics in 2 ml of culture solution. At this high concentration, 1000 nm and 2000 nm microplastics also decreased the survival rate to approximately 50% compared to no microplastics negative control (Figure 3). However, statistical analysis using one-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni correction indicated that these reductions were not statistically significant. The Student's *t*-test *p*-value between the no-treatment group and the 20 μ L of 100 nm microplastics group was 0.00965, which is below 0.05 but above the Bonferroni-corrected threshold of 0.0003. All other *p*-values from pairwise comparisons with the no-treatment condition were higher than 0.0003. These results may be due to high variability within the group and suggest the need for further experiments under more controlled settings.

The microplastic beads were all observed inside the gut of water fleas, both dead and alive (Figure 4). Especially, dead water fleas were covered with microplastics both inside and outside of the body, which suggests that too much of microplastics damaged the animals.

Finally, we examined whether excreta of mealworms fed with Styrofoam affect human intestinal cell line Caco-2 cells. After collecting excreta of mealworms, they were mixed with organic solvent such as dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) or ethanol (EtOH). Then, the solutions were added to the Caco-2 cell cultures. Excreta from mealworms fed with normal food were

also tested. None of the tested conditions reduced the cell viability of Caco-2, except for the condition with a high concentration of EtOH (Figure 5). Compared to the no-treatment control, the reduction of cell viability in the high concentration of EtOH condition was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). However, comparisons between vehicle controls (DMSO or EtOH) and the corresponding excreta solutions dissolved in the same solvents showed no statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$). Statistical analysis was conducted using one-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni correction to account for multiple pairwise comparisons among the 12 experimental conditions. Therefore, these results suggest that excreta from mealworms, either fed with normal food or only Styrofoam, do not exhibit cytotoxic effects on Caco-2 cells.

Figure 1. Effects of microplastics on the growth of barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) and ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*) seedlings. Microplastic beads of different sizes (100 nm, 1000 nm, and 2000 nm in diameter) and surface charges (positive and negative) were used to assess their impact on plant growth. After incubating seeds in the presence of 2% microplastic beads for 12 days, the fresh weight (blue columns) and stem length (grey lines) of the seedlings were measured. Data represent average values from 10 seedlings in a single experimental set. As a negative control, seeds were grown in distilled water (none).

Figure 2. Fluorescence microscopy images of barley roots after 12-day incubation in the presence of various microplastic beads with different sizes (100 nm, 1000 nm, and 2000 nm in diameter) and surface charges (negative and positive). Fluorescence images were captured using appropriate filter sets with excitation and emission wavelengths matched to the specific fluorescent tags attached to the microplastic beads.

Figure 3. Survival rate of water flea (*Daphnia* spp.) after two days of incubation in culture solution with or without microplastics. Water fleas were incubated in 2 ml of culture solution, and microplastic bead solutions (10, 15, and 20 µL) were added to the respective treatment groups. The no-treatment control (non) and conditions treated with negatively charged microplastics are shown in blue, while conditions treated with positively charged microplastics are shown in red. The graph presents the average survival rate and standard error from three independent experiments.

Figure 4. Fluorescence microscopy images of water fleas after 2 days of incubation with microplastics. Microplastic beads of varying sizes (100, 1000, and 2000 nm in diameter) and surface charges (negative and positive) were used. For each condition, representative images of individual water fleas are shown, highlighting the presence of fluorescently tagged microplastics within the body, primarily in the gut.

Figure 5. Cell viability of Caco-2 cells after three days of incubation with various solutions. Styr is mealworm excretions after feeding Styrofoam only. Food is mealworm excretions after feeding normal food. DMSO and EtOH are organic solvents that were added to the excretions. The high amount of excretion (30 mg) and the low amount of excretion (15 mg) were represented with [high] and [low], respectively. The absence of additional solution was depicted as non. The high concentration of ethanol ([high] EtOH) was used as a positive control for reduced cell viability. Both vehicle controls were used (EtOH and DMSO). Data are average and standard error from three independent experiments.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we investigated the effects of microplastics on a range of biological systems, including plants, aquatic and terrestrial animals. Polystyrene microplastic beads of various sizes (100, 1000, and 2000 nm in diameter) and surface charges (positive from amine modification, or negative from sulfate or carboxylate modification) were applied to germinating seeds of barley and ryegrass, as well as water fleas (*Daphnia* spp.). The addition of microplastic beads to moist filter papers where seeds were germinating did not significantly inhibit seedling growth, as shown by similar plant weight and stem length across conditions. This result was unexpected, especially given that microplastic beads was detected not only on the root surfaces but also within plant tissues. In contrast, exposure to positively charged microplastics significantly reduced the viability of water fleas, with 100 nm microplastic beads showing the most pronounced effect. This finding aligns with the observed ingestion of microplastics by the water fleas.

To explore potential human health implications, mealworms were fed exclusively with Styrofoam, a form of polystyrene, and then, their excreta were dissolved in an organic solvent and added to the cultured human Caco-2 cells. Since this cell line has been used as a model of intestinal epithelial cells, this experiment was intended to simulate human exposure to potential microplastic degradation byproducts. No significant cytotoxic effects were observed in Caco-2 cells under the tested conditions. Future studies may explore the effects of different solvents and concentrations on Caco-2 cells, as well as similar experiments using other human cell types. In addition, the excreta of mealworms fed only with Styrofoam can be chemically characterized to assess polymer degradation, using analytical instruments such as gel permeation chromatography, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy¹⁵. Changes in the gut microbiota of mealworms due to plastic consumption could also be examined using 16S rRNA sequencing.

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Author Contributions

Y.J., M.S., and M.K. conducted the experiments and data analysis and contributed to the drafting of the manuscript. K.Y.P. contributed to the conception, design, data analysis, and drafting the manuscript.

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